

SENSORIAL GROUPS AS A TOOL TO INTEGRATE THE EMOTIONAL DIMENSION IN DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

Designing products that satisfy consumers requires information gathered through the human senses. This paper presents a “multisensory guideline for design”, a new tool proposed for emotional product design. These guidelines were based on the identification and study of human sensorial preference groups, and how they relate to the aesthetic qualities of products.

In order to integrate this tool in the design process, we have identified different human sensorial groups and ten aspects or attributes associated with the characteristics and peculiarities that can be used to design a product. The association of ten sensorial attributes with the sensorial groups made possible the integration of the “multisensory guidelines for design”.

The guidelines were tested using one product (computer mouse), focusing on one sense and a human sensorial group, and the evaluation was carried out by presenting three different models and control samples to 55 different users.

KEYWORDS: *Sensorial groups; emotions, senses, tools for design*

INTRODUCTION

Designing products to satisfy consumers requires information gathered through the human senses. Human senses can be seen as part of a structure, which determines the physical and psycho-emotional interaction the user has with an object. The senses involve a complete set of innate and learned psychological responses that can be graded, and which allow living beings to connect with the surrounding environment and interpret stimuli in order to react to and survive in their natural environment.

The senses allow the user to live, experiment and, as a result, evaluate their experience with both the environment and products. “Sensory systems allow people to perceive a product and assess what kind of product it is. They provide feedback on people’s actions. Furthermore, they tell a person whether a sensation (visual, auditory, tactual, olfactory, or gustatory) is pleasurable or should be avoided” (Schifferstein, Hekkert, 2008, p. 3). Therefore, the sensorial systems are the structures and processes that determine customer’s preferences.

Sensorial science started to be developed when the importance of understanding sensorial phenomena was recog-

nized. It links scientific and technological disciplines that are concerned with sensorial perceptions and their relation to products like food, viticulture, cosmetics, car production and other industrial objects such as household and office products (Daban, 2002). This permits the development of a new generation of industrial products.

Some works focused on the analysis of the product experience (Schifferstein & Hekkert, 2008) and the human emotional aspect in the product design (Norman 2004); (Jordan 2002) consider directly and indirectly the presence and relevance of the human senses. They are explained based on the reception and processing of the information levels provided by the object to the user through the senses and at the same time with the sensorial election code elements, considered determinant in the present work.

Another study in the field of product design, called Kansei Engineering (also known as Emotion Engineering) was proposed by Nagamichi (1988), who mentioned the importance of taking into account the desirable features of the product perceived by the end users through their senses. A few examples of how this methodology may be used in product development can be found in: (Schüte, *et al.*, 2008, Kyungmee, Changrim 2007, Lee, *et al.*, 2008) .

Some companies and designers have already developed research that conceives of and explores several methods to introduce product desirable features perceived by users through their senses. This research seeks to identify the affective preferences and the emotional perceptions of the user. The research conceives of methodologies based on the attainment of adjectival descriptions, of expert and non-expert subjects (or customers) of the tested products.

For instance, Renault carried out experiments that include the tactile sensations behind the steering wheel (Crochemore & Nesa, 2004) and the car brake systems (Dairou *et al.*, 2010), Crochemore and Nesa (2004), used “Cartography of the preferences” and (Dairou *et al.*, 2003) “flash profile” (derived of the Free Choice Profiling from the field of sensorial evaluation of food) as a preliminary study to research the feasibility of the car brake systems description. On the other hand, Peugeot basically studies seats and dashboards (Egoroff, 2005) using the “hierarchical sorting task”. Cosmetics (Coronel *et al.*, 2003) and phones (Lorbo *et al.*, 2003) have also been re-evaluated by similar methodologies.

Regarding the marketing process, sensorial marketing (Rieuner, 2002) was presented on sales points as part of the experiential marketing trend. It evokes emotions via stimulation of the five senses by attributes that are complimentary to the product (fragrances, music, images).

Even though the sensorial approach, as a theme, has been partially developed, there are specific areas that can be explored.

In this article we propose a tool named multisensory guidelines for design (Bedolla, 2002) for product design based on users’ preferences, derived from their senses. These guidelines are based on the human sensorial group identification and study, based on research related to physiology and human perception psychology and how the group relates to the product's aesthetic qualities meaning the different sensorial features of the product.

These guidelines allow the designer to:

- Meet the specific emotional and functional requirements of different and defined user groups.
- Know the specific sensorial attributes to apply to the products, satisfying the particular emotional and functional requirements of different groups of users recognized in the guidelines.
- Have a tool to complement the existing methods of contemporary design.

GUIDELINES FOR MULTISENSORY DESIGN: THE PRELIMINARY STUDIES

Human senses can be seen to be the structures that determine the physical and psycho-emotional interaction a user has with an object. Initially, the information reaches the sense organs (eyes, nose, ears and skin). The information is then delivered to the central nervous system and, eventually,

to the brain cortex. In the latter region, the individual makes her first pleasurable judgment based on the quality of the interaction (the use of different sensorial modalities) and its intensity (the impetus of the perception) (Guirao, 1980; Bermejo, 1981). This then continues through the limbic system and is channeled through other innate preferences as well as the memory. These determine the affective/cognitive evaluation the user makes as a result of the interaction with the object.

Therefore emotion is the dynamic syncopation of different cognitive and biological appreciations. Sensorial perception can be understood as the first filter in the emotional chain, which will eventually be transformed into more complex feelings and desires (Ortony *et al.*, 1996).

The Human Sensorial Groups

Based on the principle that senses allow the user to live, experiment and, as a result, evaluate the products, we studied the human sensorial perceptual process. By analyzing the perceptual process we identified the existence of determining factors which establish the sensorial capacities, and the individual differences in terms of preference for sensory information and the level of stimulation in the different human groups.

According to research related to physiology and human perception psychology, the different capacities, requirements, preferences and psycho-emotional demands of human groups will depend on a series of dimensions that comprise the person entirely (Bermejo, 1981; Buck & Buck, 1984; Plutchik, 1985; Rusell, Woudzia, 1986; Fernández, 1999). The first group of these dimensions belongs to the human’s internal boundary (related to the human’s organic component), and the second group belongs to the person’s external boundary (related to the environment where a person lives) (Munari, 1995; Quarante 1992). The dimensions of the internal boundary comprise the person’s personality tendency, gender, and age. The dimensions of the external boundary comprise the person’s culture, society, family, the raising environment, and the daily environment.

Based on these studies the human sensorial groups were classified as follows:

- **Four age groups:** the elderly, adults, adolescents and children (Craig, 1992; Goebel, 1981; Tyler, 1975). The age of the person determines the stage of development of the sensorial system (nervous system and peripheral sense organs), as well as physiological and psycho emotional demands. The physical and emotional sensory requirements are common to all the age groups determined by elements of their physiological nature and emotional being. However, the degree of their physiological nature and emotional being which determines the capacities and sensorial requirements according to the age of the individual will be diverse.
- **Two personality groups:** introverted and extroverted. These are determined by innate temperament and seem to depend on the nervous system. Introversion and extroversion require different kinds of sensorial stimulation. The

level demanded will depend on the degree of introversion or extroversion of the users. Even if all people have some elements of both personality groups, the individual tends to have more of one of them and to react according to these characteristics in certain situations, more than with other personality tendencies (Sheldon, 1970; Kretschmer, 1970; Eysenck, 2006).

- **Two gender groups:** women and men. Gender responds to physiological processes such as hormones and other organic processes. Women usually have sharper senses, except for sight, and develop a more sensitive nervous system. Biological differences can also be accentuated by the affections, stereotypes, and the different social roles determined by gender. However, these social roles are diversifying in response to economic and socio-cultural changing norms (Burg & Hulbert, 1961; Clark & Mehl, 1971; Baker, 1987; Hyde, 1995).

HUMAN GENDER	
Female	Male
Visual Sensorial Requirements	Visual Sensorial Requirements
Females have twice the ability of the males to recognize and distinguish surface qualities of the objects, especially the light reflection or gloss. This characteristic can be applied to products conceived for this human group considering surface qualities such as glowing colour or polished surfaces.	Males have two times less ability than females in recognizing and distinguishing surface qualities of objects, especially the light reflection or gloss. This characteristic can be applied to products conceived for this human group, using opaque or dull colours.
Tactile Sensorial Requirements	Tactile Sensorial Requirements
In general the tactile perceptions of this group are very high. They are especially sensitive to vibration and tactile pressure. These characteristics can be applied to products made of smooth textures.	The tactile perceptions of this group are less than the females, especially in the area of vibration. These characteristics can be applied to products considered the most easily identifiable bold textures, such as grainy, rough or corrugated.

Table 1. Examples of the sensorial requirements of the gender groups
Source: Bedolla (2002)

The Sensorial Attributes

The study of how human sensorial groups relate to aesthetic qualities, as mentioned, seeks to recognize how different sen-

social features, when applied to object design, are capable of satisfying different user groups' preferences.

Considering the manufactured object we identified its sensorial features as the key elements that define its characteristics and uses (Manzini, 1993). Its sensorial features being those humans can perceive (Gimeno, 1986).

Therefore we have identified ten aspects or attributes associated with the characteristics and peculiarities of the different sensorial human groups. These attributes are visual: form, color and graphics; tactile: form, temperature, texture, weight and movement; olfactory: odors; and auditory - ambient sounds and music. Each one of the attributes has a specific effect on the user, which allows human sensorial requirements and characteristics to be satisfied.

There are specific effects we identified studying several researches to each attribute. The emotional effects of the visual attributes as the form and the decorative graphics are explained mainly in agreement with diverse authors (Sander *et al.*, 1969; Gombrich, 2000; Arnheim, 2004). Because our perceptive system is based on laws or mental superstructures, it stands out that the Gestalt theory of expression that is based on the principle of the isomorphism, supposes that a relation between the physical forces of the observed object exists: form, size, movement, etc., also the psychic dynamics of the observer, so that the features of the form influence in many ways the conduct and mood of the observer.

Moreover, a number of papers concerning colours (Goethe, 2006; Kandinsky, 2001; Ferrer, 1999) have progressed a theory that these stimulants produce certain physiological effects in individuals, due to physiological aspects. Just as the constitution of the human visual perception process of colours — with the central participation of the nervous system — in the same form produces certain psychological effects due to the element of nature, kingdom, body or substance that is always presented in indestructible association with the colour. These characteristics of the colours are going to allow them contemporarily to have important emotional and physical benefits for a person.

In relation to tactile features, it has been shown that they have a positive influence on both the mental and physical health of the user through the skin by means of the expression of texture, temperature, the weight and other elements that relate in an important way to the senses, like the movement, the pressure and the form through the objects, (Oñativia, 1972).

Auditory features are basically transmitted through vibrations. These create a physiological effect that enables the user to synchronize with the object, producing some physiological transformations (reduction or production of anxiety, high or low respiratory and cardiac rates, reduction or elevation of the sanguineous tension, and the reduction of stress hormones, among others) (Tomatis, 1978, 1991). Psychologically these effects are explained because the auditory information is received from the environment in several levels of abstraction and meaning, which also acquires certain impli-

EXTROVERT TENDENCIES			
General Sensorial Characteristics	Sensorial Features	Sensorial Features Involved	Expressed In the Product
<p>Tendency to seek strong sensorial stimuli. Strong nervous system, high threshold. They need more energy to appreciate sensorial stimuli.</p> <p>Less receptive if relaxed and more receptive if active or positively stressed.</p> <p>Seekers of sensation and new stimuli.</p>	<p>They prefer and are more sensitive to colors than shapes.</p> <p>They seek to please sight, smell and touch. They prefer complex and schematic figures.</p> <p>In their most primitive form they are a good eaters and enjoy taking the sun; the more sophisticated prefer an atmosphere of friendship and art</p>	<p>Visual (Colors and forms), Scents and Textures.</p>	<p>Strongly characterized products flamboyant, Shifting, varied.</p> <p>Greater use of colours.</p>

Table 2. Sensorial features (to be included in the object) correlated to sensorial characteristics in extroverted personalities
Source: Bedolla (2002)

cations on what is happening or will happen; in this way the sounds are associated to determined ideas, sensations, emotional states, etc. (Alcalde, 1988).

Smells have a considerable influence on the emotional states, motivations, and health. This influence is explained mainly due to the process of perception of the sense of smell. Thus the sense of smell is strongly influenced by the limbic system (located in the brain) and the properties of the smells since there are active and relaxing scents (Van Toller, Dodd, 1988).

Guideline Integration

The integration of the guidelines was based, as mentioned earlier, on how human sensorial groups relate to the aesthetic qualities of a product. These relations should henceforth be used as tools that allow the designer to distinguish users' preferences together with aesthetic and functional features of the product. This should facilitate innovation in design and lead to the creation of sensitively designed objects. That is to say, it should help bring users closer to their natural preferences and needs. The following figure gives an example of the integrated guidelines (Figure 1) (Table 2).

Guideline Usage and Tests

The purpose of this study was to put into practice and test some of the guidelines. We chose the guidelines related to the personality tendencies (introversion and extroversion). The guidelines were tested using one product (computer mouse), focusing on one sense: the tactile. The main objective was to know if people who present introvert or extrovert tendencies of personality prefer the product (mouse) redesigned based on the guidelines conceived. The evaluation was carried out by presenting three different models and control samples to 55 different users.

Figure 1. Sensorial attributes correlated to extroversion personalities

The Process of Sensorial Redesigning of the Mice

The mouse was chosen as the experimental object because it is used daily by the participants chosen to test the product. Only one kind of sensorial attribute was taken into consideration for the re-designing process: tactility (form, size, and texture), so as to simplify the test and because touch is a form of direct experience useful for product evaluation. We used the touch information during product evaluation, the hand is the principal source of input to the touch perceptual system, and therefore the hand was proposed as the organ of touch called a person's outer brain.

Some of the main physical and emotional sensorial requirements considered that belong to people who tend to possess a predominant extrovert personality include: the application of sensorial attributes for a hard, vigorously sensorial stimulation, and the need of more energy to appreciate the stimulation of the senses. Extroverts present a major sensibility and preference for visual stimulation, especially to attributes such as colors and complex forms.

In contrast, people that possess a predominant introverted personality tend to reject and dislike strong sensorial stimulation. They need small quantities of energy to appreciate stimulation. They present major sensibility and preferences for tactile stimulation rather than other senses.

In the following table (table 3) we are describing the sensorial attributes of touch used for each group shown in the personality guidelines:

Figure 2. Mouse labeled A, designed with the guidelines for female gender, ages ranged from 18 to 45, and extroverted personalities: organic form, medium size, and with a slightly rugged texture.

SENSORIAL ATTRIBUTES OF TOUCH USED FOR EACH GROUP SHOWN IN THE PERSONALITY GUIDELINES		
Touch Attributes Used for the Extroverted Personality		
Form	Textures	Weight
Shapes and asymmetric characteristics give rise to dynamic sensations for added energy to appreciate stimulation: organic, irregular, undefined shapes, decentralized elements, elongated, shifted.	The idea of being entertained and playful is expressed through textures made up of an infinite number of small, dynamic, and heterogeneous structures.	Lightness because it is lively, active, agile and dynamic. The concept is represented plastically by small or medium sized objects
Touch Attributes Used for the Introverted Personality		
Form	Textures	Weight
Small, compact, refined, round, organic, harmonious proportions with rhythmic contours.	Adaptable and flexible. They must be smooth with homogenous surfaces and convey warmth (for example furry objects) and convey moderate freshness (slight ruggedness or granularity).	A little heavy, because that transmits an idea of durable goods. A large, thick, medium, or large sized object represents the concept plastically.

Table 3. Sensorial attributes of touch Used for each group showed in the personality guidelines

Four computer mouse were designed and labeled as A, B, C and D:

- Two mouse labeled as A were designed. The first one was designed using the guideline for extrovert personalities, and the second one using the guideline for introvert personalities. The goal of this study was, (already mentioned) to put into practice and test some of the guidelines.

The particular attributes of the mouse designed, were selected from the guidelines for extroverted personalities: organic form, medium size, and with a slightly rugged texture (Figure 2). Because the touch attributes were the ones to be evaluated a neutral color was used.

The specific sensorial characteristics used for the mouse designed with the guidelines for introvert personalities were: geometric and symmetric form, smooth texture and medium

size. Because the touch attributes were the ones to be evaluated, a neutral color was used (Figure 3).

- Mouse B was randomly modified ignoring the guidelines.

The sensorial characteristics used were: blunt edges on the lower part, plain surface, and medium size. Because the touch attributes were going to be evaluated, a neutral color was used.

- Mouse C was randomly modified ignoring the guidelines.

The sensorial characteristics used were: slight organic curves, with a texture that emphasizes the curves, and a small size. Because the touch attributes were going to be evaluated, a neutral color was used.

- Finally, an ordinary white mouse was labeled as D.

Figure 3. Mouse labeled A designed with the guidelines for female gender, ages ranged from 18 to 45, and introvert personalities: geometric and symmetric form, smooth texture and medium size. Because the touch attributes were the ones to be evaluated, a neutral color was used

Method

The method for eliciting the sensorial information from the user is known as the selection method, or the pluralist or relativist approach. The users interact with the object and describe their preferences.

Participants included a sample of 55 users, whose ages ranged from 18 to 45, from the Mixtec Technological University, Oaxaca, Mexico. Participants included students, administrative staff, and academics from the University.

Results

In the following tables (tables 4, 5) we are describing the results of the test to know if people who present introvert or extrovert tendencies of personality prefer the product (mouse) redesigned based on the guidelines conceived for them.

RESULTS OF THE TEST	
Redesigned mouse through the introvert personality guideline	
<p align="center">User preference reaction to the redesigned mouse Out of the 28 users identified with introverted personalities: 18 preferred the guideline redesigned mouse A, 2 preferred the randomly modified mouse B, 5 preferred the randomly modified mouse C, 3 preferred the ordinary mouse D</p>	
Mouse preferred by users identified with introverted personality	Order of importance of the qualities of the redesigned mouse that were preferred by users
Mouse A	Out of the 28 users 18 users preferred mouse A: 6 preferred it because of the form, 9 users preferred it because of the texture, 3 users preferred it because of the size
Mouse B	2 users preferred mouse B because of the texture
Mouse C	5 users identified with introvert personalities preferred mouse C: 3 preferred it because of the texture, 2 preferred it because of the form

Table 4. Results of the test for redesigned mouse through the introvert personality guideline

RESULTS OF THE TEST	
Redesigned mouse through the extrovert personality guideline	
<p align="center">User preference reaction to the redesigned mouse Out of the 27 users identified with an extrovert personality: 9 preferred the guideline-redesigned mouse A, 14 preferred the randomly modified mouse B, 1 preferred the randomly modified mouse C, 3 preferred the mouse D</p>	
Mouse preferred by users identified with an extrovert personality	Order of importance of the qualities of the redesigned mouse that were preferred by users
Mouse A	Out of 9 extroverts who preferred mouse A, 6 preferred it because of the form, 3 preferred it because of the size
Mouse B	Out of the 14 users identified with extrovert personality who preferred mouse B, 13 preferred it because of the form, 1 preferred it because of the size
Mouse C	The person who preferred mouse C preferred it because of the form
Mouse D	3 users preferred mouse D because of the form

Table 5. Results of the test for redesigned mouse through the extrovert personality guideline

Methodology for the Analysis of the Results

The social network analysis (Freeman, 2004) is a powerful tool that enables scientists to recognize certain behaviours and group patterns related to different social structures. It studies the relationships of actors (individuals or groups) in many different contexts. Information can be elicited from both individuals (micro level) and groups (macro level). Moreover, the method uses a resource known as “graph theory” that runs software analysis tools named Pajek. This allows a mathematical analysis of the relations between individuals and organizations in many different fields of knowledge. It is a powerful 32-bit program designed for a Windows operating system and used for the analysis of large networks.

Figure 4 gives the results of the test. It shows the mathematical model (network) that resulted from introducing our variables.

In figure 4 there is a net composed of 63 nodes. 55 of these nodes have an elliptical form. These represent the volunteers divided into two categories: introverted and extroverted. There are four triangular shapes, which represent the mice, and four rectangles, which represent the preferred qualities. The grade that each volunteer gave to each of the sensorial features was taken as the value that relates the user and each characteristic. Moreover, the relation between each volunteer and their preferred mouse was given the value of one.

When considering the value of these relations as a form of differentiation, Pajek allows us to see the rate of influence

each feature has on the participants. As the system takes into account the value of every relation in order to determine its position, those qualities that were graded similarly can be seen in the central part of the net (such as the form of the mouse). Size, for example, can be located closer to the nodes that represent the volunteers that preferred mouse A than to those that preferred another mouse. This means that this second quality was preferred. Likewise, it may be observed that form and size are more important than texture to those who choose mouse B.

Discussion

For the users identified with introverted personalities it can be seen that the guideline-redesigned mouse was preferred to the other three models, therefore, for this group of users, the introverted personality guideline was allowed to know the group of touch attributes (form, size and texture), which are capable of leading the product preferences. The quality preferred for them was texture (touch attribute).

However, as was observed, the tactile evaluation changed the preferences of the extroverted personalities towards mouse B. The quality preferred was form. Upon considering the preference of visual stimulation among other senses for this group, the quality preferred by them was visual and touch attributes. Thus we can infer that it is a strong influence of the visual sense and may be the cause of mouse B being preferred by extroverted users, rather than mouse A.

Based on this result, we can suppose that for our test, that

Figure 4. This network or mathematical model shows the preferences of 55 users concerning 4 specially designed mice (shown in nodes with the text mouse A, B, C or D). The users have been characterized as introverted or extroverted. In the centre the grade or level in which each sensorial attribute reflected in the mice generated particular preferences may be seen.

touch attributes had enough influence to lead product preference of the introvert user group. Moreover we can confirm that this group of users has preference for tactile stimulation (among other senses) because they preferred texture, which is a tactile attribute.

It is considered necessary to undertake more studies to re-evaluate and validate the relevance of touch attributes presented in the guideline for extrovert personality. We recommend incorporating visual attributes in the redesign, taking advantage of the correspondence between sensations derived from the human multisensory perception named synaesthesia, since it exists, as an innate human nature, a visual and tactile sensation complementation or correspondence. The quality preferred by the introvert user group was texture. This preference revealed its inclination towards tactile stimulation, rather than other senses. The second quality preferred was size, and the least preferred quality by this group was form.

For the extrovert user group, who preferred visual stimulation, the first quality preferred by them was form, due to its simultaneous visual and tactile nature. This preference for visual stimulation among other senses reveals for them the quality or attribute preferred in the mouse evaluation was form, due to its major visual components. Second quality preferred was size, at least texture (touch quality).

CONCLUSIONS

Upon considering previous studies and the proposals of several authors, the innovation of the “multisensory guidelines for design” permits to identify definite requirements, characteristics, and preferences of the people, which lead us to make out different sensorial groups of users. Moreover, the multisensory guidelines for design translate these specific human sensorial requirements, characteristics, and preferences into concrete multisensory qualities or attributes of design, which can be expressed through the five senses in the product design for definite groups of users.

The first test of some of the guidelines (personality tendencies) presented in this paper show that the personality characteristics are related to the preferences of the product designed.

Further tests are also required in order to continue and complete the evaluation of the guidelines and validate them.

This research found evidence that the specific or precise sensorial characteristics, capacities and requirements affect the preference of a product. The guidelines should represent an instrument (a complementary projection tool) to provide some criteria in applying the sensorial attributes of products. The sensorial and aesthetic product attributes can be used in a logical and appropriate way to correspond to the sensorial necessities and characteristics of a specific user group.

This new framework improves the possibility of recognizing

human preferences and the needs of specific groups of users. From the manufacturer’s point of view, the application of this method should enable him/her to diversify models and specialize in particular sectors of society.

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